

Groin Configurations: An Approach towards Stable Lowland Rivers with Improved Environmental Functions

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Abstract : Dynamicity of stream channels along with environmental concern is the key issue to address in lowland rivers like Jamuna in Bangladesh. The groins are important structures in attaining the improved river environment, but their effective functioning is not evident yet with the present design. Considering the present demands, an approach through modification of groin configurations is planned to function more natural way in dynamic lowland rivers. Four different configurations including the conventional one are considered in the study, and the changes in hydro- and morphodynamics affected by various structures are investigated in the laboratory. Results show that the modified combined groin favors gradual deceleration of flow towards the channel side and minimizes local scour noticeably. This favors stable regular channel and improve environmental functions.

Keywords : Lowland river, dynamicity, river environment, groin configuration, local scour

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